

Task 4.2A (subtask 3): Enhance BioPortal's SKOS support to facilitate ontology reuse, improve maintainability, and simplify representation of value sets

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
2025-07-23	v1	Document created by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	Document created
2025-07-25	v1.1	Document written by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	First draft completed
2025-07-31	v1.2	Revised and approved by the Stanford University team.	

Purpose

The RADx Data Hub integrates BioPortal's biomedical ontologies to improve the clarity and consistency of metadata associated with studies and data files. By leveraging BioPortal [1,2] terminologies, the Data Hub enhances the accuracy and interoperability of study data, making it easier to share and analyze information across diverse research efforts.

Task 4.2A focuses on developing enhancements to BioPortal's term functionality to support ontology discovery, improve comprehension of ontology terms, and encourage the reuse of ontologies and terms within the RADx research community and the broader scientific ecosystem.

Subtask 3 (also referred to as 4.2A-3) involves implementing improvements on both the backend API and the user interface (UI), specifically targeting BioPortal's ability to process and present Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) ontologies more effectively to the wider community.

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Introduction

The RADx Data Hub utilizes BioPortal's extensive collection of biomedical ontologies to standardize and ensure consistent metadata across its wide range of studies. For RADx researchers and users, having access to a well-established resource like BioPortal is essential, not only for maintaining metadata consistency but also for improving the usability and navigability of the data.

BioPortal currently hosts over 100 SKOS ontologies and vocabularies, many of which are actively used by the RADx Data Hub community. Task 4.2A-3 introduces a series of enhancements to BioPortal's support for SKOS, aimed at improving the handling, processing, and display of SKOS-based ontologies and terminologies. These updates are designed to make SKOS content more accessible and reusable for RADx researchers working across diverse biomedical datasets.

BioPortal's model architecture now includes SKOS-specific artifacts such as **Schemes**, **Collections**, and **SKOS eXtension Labels (SKOS-XL)**, along with support for internal mappings. These mappings enable SKOS metadata to be pre-populated with values provided by the user in the ontology source file.

The public-facing BioPortal API has been updated with new endpoints that return all schemes and collections for a given SKOS ontology. Additionally, the existing term and term roots endpoints have been enhanced to allow filtering of results based on specified SKOS schemes and/or collections.

To take advantage of these new API capabilities, several improvements to the BioPortal UI have been implemented to better support the display and navigation of SKOS ontologies. New tabs have been added to BioPortal's term display, allowing separate viewing of Schemes and Collections within SKOS ontologies, with an option to sort terms by the date they were added to the ontology.

The following sections describe these improvements in detail.

SKOS Model & API Enhancements

The latest update introduces a new set of models in the BioPortal middleware that support more granular storage and manipulation of SKOS artifacts. Previously, the

model layer included a general **Class** model that was used to represent terms in any ontology. While generally robust, this model did not account for all the specific attributes associated with the SKOS construct known as **Concept**. This gap has now been filled, allowing SKOS concepts to be fully explored. Figure 1 shows a REST API call to the existing BioPortal `/classes` endpoint, which now supports filtering SKOS concepts to include only those that belong to the specified scheme(s):


```
[
- {
  prefLabel: "degree of precision",
  - synonym: [
    "degree of accuracy"
  ],
  - inScheme: [
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_23256,
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE
  ],
  - isInactiveScheme: [
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_23256
  ],
  memberOf: [ ],
  isInActiveCollection: [ ],
  @id: http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/c_16416,
  @type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept
},
- {
  prefLabel: "morphological trait",
  - synonym: [
    "morphological characteristic"
  ],
  - inScheme: [
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_23256,
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE
  ],
  - isInactiveScheme: [
    http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_23256
  ],
  ...
}
```

Figure 1: BioPortal `/classes` endpoint filtering concepts by SKOS Concept Schemes. Only classes whose `skos:inScheme` property matches the provided scheme ID(s) are returned. The endpoint accepts a parameter called `concept_schemes`, which takes a URL-encoded list of scheme IDs to filter results. In this example, the results are filtered on the Scheme ID http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_23256:

https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/classes/roots?concept_schemes=http%3A%2F%2Fopendata.inrae.fr%2FthesaurusINRAE%2Fmt_23256

A **SKOS Concept Scheme** groups SKOS concepts that belong to the same vocabulary, thesaurus, or classification system. In contrast, a **SKOS Collection** is a labeled, non-hierarchical grouping of related concepts, typically used for presentation or navigation.

To support these SKOS constructs, two new API endpoints were added for SKOS ontologies. The `/schemes` endpoint returns all concept schemes defined within an ontology, exposing its high-level structure. The `/collections` endpoint lists all SKOS collections, enabling interfaces to organize and display related concepts in user-friendly groupings. Figures 2 and 3 show examples of a REST API call that returns all schemes and collections for a given SKOS ontology/vocabulary.

```

[
  - {
    prefLabel: "ORG taxonomic classification of organisms",
    @id: http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt\_26190,
    @type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme,
    - links: {
      self: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/schemes/http%3A%2F%2Fopendata.inrae.fr%2FthesaurusINRAE%2Fmt\_26190,
      roots: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/classes\_concept\_scheme=http%3A%2F%2Fopendata.inrae.fr%2FthesaurusINRAE%2Fmt\_26190,
      ontology: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/,
    - @context: {
      self: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme,
      roots: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept,
      ontology: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology
    }
  },
  - @context: {
    @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/,
    prefLabel: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel,
    @language: "en"
  }
},
- {
  prefLabel: "ENV water management",
  @id: http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt\_18,
  @type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme,
  - links: {
    self: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/schemes/http%3A%2F%2Fopendata.inrae.fr%2FthesaurusINRAE%2Fmt\_18,
    roots: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/classes\_concept\_scheme=http%3A%2F%2Fopendata.inrae.fr%2FthesaurusINRAE%2Fmt\_18,
    ontology: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/,
  - @context: {
    self: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme,
    roots: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept,
    ontology: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology
  }
},
- @context: {
  @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/,
  prefLabel: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel,
  @language: "en"
}
},
},
]

```

Figure 2: BioPortal :skos_ontology/schemes endpoint returning ALL schemes for a given SKOS ontology


```
[
- {
  prefLabel: "coll MAPPED TO MESH",
  memberCount: 1161,
  @id: http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/gr\_7f1b79e6,
  @type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Collection,
  - links: {
    self:
      https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/collections/ht
    ,
    members:
      https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/collections/ht
    ,
    ontology: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES,
    - @context: {
      self: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Collection,
      members: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept,
      ontology: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology
    }
  },
  - @context: {
    @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/,
    prefLabel: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel,
    @language: "en"
  }
},
- {
  prefLabel: "coll MAPPED TO AGROVOC",
  memberCount: 1074,
  @id: http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/gr\_17778f51,
  @type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Collection,
  - links: {
    self:
      https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/collections/ht
    ,
    members:
      https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES/collections/ht
    ,
    ontology: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES,
    - @context: {
      self: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Collection,
      members: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept,
      ontology: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology
    }
  },
  - @context: {
    @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/,
    prefLabel: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel,
    @language: "en"
  }
},
],
```

Figure 3: BioPortal :skos_ontology/collections endpoint returning ALL collections for a given SKOS ontology

New SKOS user interface

To support the new functionality the Stanford team has built around SKOS ontologies, the term display UI has been redesigned to offer users an opportunity to explore the SKOS specific artifacts. When viewing a SKOS ontology, the term homepage now includes two additional tabs: Schemes tab and Collections tab. Clicking on these tabs yields the corresponding view. Figures 4 and 5 show the corresponding Schemes and Collections views belonging to the French National Research Institute for Agriculture Thesaurus ontology (INRAE) [3].

The screenshot displays the BioPortal interface for the INRAE Thesaurus ontology. The browser address bar shows the URL `stage.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES?p=schemes`. The page header includes the BioPortal logo and navigation links for Ontologies, Search, Annotator, Recommender, and Mappings, along with Login and Support buttons. The main content area is titled "INRAE Thesaurus" and indicates it was last updated on July 16, 2025. A navigation bar below the title contains tabs for Summary, Concepts, Properties, Schemes (highlighted with a red box), Collections, Notes, Mappings, and Widgets. The Schemes tab is active, showing a list of concept schemes on the left and a details panel on the right. The list includes "AGR agricultural machinery and equipment" (highlighted) and various biological categories like "AGR agricultural products", "AGR animal husbandry and breeding", etc. The details panel for the selected scheme shows the ID `http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/mt_26190`, the preferred name "ORG taxonomic classification of organisms", and the type `http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme`. Below the details is a section for "All Properties".

Figure 4: User interface for browsing SKOS Concept Schemes within an ontology.

Figure 5: User interface for browsing SKOS Collections within an ontology.

The BioPortal UI now includes a new **Concept Date View**, which works for both SKOS and non-SKOS ontologies. This feature allows users to browse ontology terms based on when they were created or last modified, organizing concepts chronologically under headings like “July 2025” or “June 2025.” This makes it easy to spot recent additions and updates at a glance. Figure 6 below shows the Date View for the INRAETHES ontology.

Figure 6: Terms in SKOS and non-SKOS ontologies can now be viewed by the date they were introduced to the ontology.

In addition to Date View, the BioPortal UI also introduces a new **Collection View**, which lets users focus on terms that belong to specific SKOS collections within an ontology. This view adds a simple filter for all available collections, so users can narrow the list to just the concepts included in one or more chosen groups. It offers another powerful way to explore and organize ontology terms, helping users quickly focus on curated, meaningful subsets of content. Figure 7 showcases the Collection View as seen when browsing the INRAETHES ontology.

Figure 7: Terms in SKOS ontologies can now be viewed by the collections they belong to.

Figures 8, 9, and 10 show examples of relevant SKOS ontologies used by the RADx Data Hub. Figure 8 depicts the RADx Data Hub Metadata Ontology (DHMO) [4] in the context of the new UI that supports SKOS artifacts. DHMO is a structured vocabulary designed to standardize how data, contributors, and metadata are described within the RADx Data Hub. As seen in the figure, DHMO now includes two additional tabs that allow separate browsing of its SKOS schemes and collections.

Figure 8: RADx Data Hub Metadata ontology (DHMO) is an example of a relevant SKOS ontology that benefits from the enhancements detailed in this report.

RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons (RADXTT-MVREASONS) [5] is another ontology example where SKOS is better suited than formats like OWL or OBO for representing hierarchical, controlled vocabularies. It standardizes the reasons why data values may be missing in RADx dataset records, grouping them under a common parent concept, *Missing Value* (-9999). Figures 9 and 10 illustrate this structure, showing the concept tree and the Schemes view of RADXTT-MVREASONS, respectively.

The screenshot shows the BioPortal interface for the 'RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons' ontology. The page title is 'RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons' with a sub-header 'Last uploaded: October 24, 2023'. The navigation bar includes 'Summary', 'Concepts', 'Properties', 'Schemes', 'Collections', 'Notes', 'Mappings', and 'Widgets'. The 'Schemes' and 'Collections' tabs are highlighted with red boxes. The left sidebar shows a search bar 'Jump to' and a list of concepts under 'Missing Value (-9999)', including 'Data Invalid (-9985)'. The right panel shows the 'Details' view for 'Data Invalid (-9985)', including its ID, preferred name, definition, synonyms, and type.

Details	
Id	https://radx.orgx/vocs/missing-value-reason/DataInvalid-9985
Preferred Name	Data Invalid (-9985)
Definitions	Data was invalid (wrong format, wrong or unknown units, not parseable, or impossible value)
Synonyms	1e
Type	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept

All Properties	
definition	Data was invalid (wrong format, wrong or unknown units, not parseable, or impossible value)
altLabel	1e
prefLabel	Data Invalid (-9985)
inScheme	https://radx.orgx/vocs/missing-value-reason

Figure 9: RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons (RADXTT-MVREASONS) is another proof of how SKOS excels at representing hierarchical controlled vocabularies, and where a detailed representation of individual SKOS artifacts adds value to the understanding, navigation, and reuse of those vocabularies within the RADx Data Hub.

Figure 10: The Schemes view of the RADXTT-MVREASONS ontology depicts its main SKOS Concept Scheme, *Missing value reasons in RADx*, which serves as the entry point for the currently defined concepts. In the future, additional schemes may be added to group concepts by other topics within the ontology.

In summary, Task 4.2A-3 delivered a major advancement in BioPortal's ability to support and display SKOS ontologies. This feature is essential for the RADx Data Hub, as it enables more effective handling and presentation of SKOS vocabularies used across the platform. On the BioPortal **backend**, new models were introduced to better represent SKOS constructs such as Concepts, Schemes, Collections, and SKOS-XL labels, along with support for internal mappings. These changes improved SKOS metadata handling and introduced new API endpoints, `/schemes` and `/collections`, to expose the organizational structure of SKOS ontologies. On the **frontend**, the BioPortal UI was updated with dedicated Schemes and Collections tabs, plus new browsing modes: **Date View** and **Collections View**. These features allow users to see when terms were added or modified and to filter terms by collection, making it easier to navigate and reuse SKOS vocabularies within the RADx Data Hub and the broader scientific community.

Resources

This section contains links to the source code developed as part of this task.

Github Repositories

- https://github.com/ncbo/bioportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ontportal/ontportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ontportal-lirimm/bioportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ncbo/ontologies_api_ruby_client

Issue Tracking

- [Enhance BioPortal's SKOS support to facilitate ontology reuse, improve maintainability, and simplify representation of value sets](#)
- [Feature: Implement the enhanced SKOS features user interface](#)
- [Feature: Add better SKOS support: Schemes, Collections, SKOS XL, SKOS metadata mappings and Concepts tree filtering](#)
- [Feature: Enhanced SKOS support, new API endpoints for Schemes, Collections, and SKOS XL labels](#)

References

[1] National Center for Biomedical Ontology. BioPortal. Accessed on July 25th, 2025. Available: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org>.

[2] Noy NF, Shah NH, Whetzel PL, Dai B, Dorf M, Griffith N, et al. BioPortal: ontologies and integrated data resources at the click of a mouse. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2009;37:W170–3. Accessed on July 25th, 2025. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp440>.

[3] French National Research Institute for Agriculture Thesaurus ontology (INRAETHES). BioPortal Staging. Accessed on July 25th, 2025. Available: <https://stage.bioontology.org/ontologies/INRAETHES>.

[4] RADx Data Hub Metadata Ontology ontology (DHMO). BioPortal. Accessed on July 25th, 2025. Available: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/DHMO>.

[5] RADx Tiger Team Missing Value Reasons ontology (RADXTT-MVREASONS). BioPortal. Accessed on July 25th, 2025. Available: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/RADXTT-MVREASONS>.